

Comparative characterisation of autotrophic and heterotrophic isopropanol formation by *Cupriavidus necator* in shake flasks

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ABSTRACT

Autotrophic cultivation offers a path to carbon-neutral bioproduction, which is increasingly valuable in the context of climate change mitigation. In this study, the production of isopropanol by *Cupriavidus necator* is used as an example for CO₂ valorisation, and a simple shake bottle system is introduced to facilitate the development of aerobic autotrophic cultivation processes and strain screening. Applying 1.5 bar overpressure in the bottle's headspace enhances gas transfer while pressure decrease was shown to be correlated to biomass and product formation, allowing to follow metabolic activity without sampling. After optimizing cultivation parameters and nickel feeding strategy, the system was applied to compare three different isopropanol-producing strains. The highest autotrophically obtained isopropanol concentration was $2.2 \pm 0.5 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ with a specific yield of $0.9 \pm 0.2 \text{ g g}_{\text{CDW}}^{-1}$ and a minimal by-product concentration of $0.05 \pm 0.01 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ acetone. Heterotrophic cultivations were carried out for comparison, obtaining up to $3.4 \pm 0.2 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ final isopropanol concentration with a specific yield of $1.4 \pm 0.1 \text{ g g}_{\text{CDW}}^{-1}$. Although the use of CO₂ instead of fructose resulted in a slower process, the overall isopropanol production is promising. This study provides valuable insights into strain behaviour while demonstrating the utility of the presented shake bottle system for advancing autotrophic process development.

1. Introduction

In a world where resources are limited but the population is growing, it is crucial, to find efficient ways to close carbon cycles and reuse former waste streams. This is especially important for gaseous industrial effluents, as they can have a negative environmental impact and contribute to global warming.

Gas fermentation is a promising approach to valorise these industrial emissions as it offers a wide range of industrial products. Furthermore, it provides key benefits, such as lower substrate costs and reduced land requirements compared to carbohydrates as a carbon source (Nangle et al., 2020). However, several bottlenecks need to be addressed before gas fermentation can be widely implemented on a large scale. These include gas transfer limitations, thermodynamic metabolic constraints, and initiating autotrophic cultivation in a laboratory setting. While commercial endeavours have been undertaken for anaerobic gas cultivations using carbon monoxide-rich streams there has been less focus on gases rich in CO₂, particularly those that also contain oxygen such as incinerator flue gas (Liew et al., 2022). Aerobic gas fermentation bears the additional need for stringent safety measures to prevent explosive

knallgas mixtures.

The first step to be taken when switching from a heterotrophic to an autotrophic cultivation is setting-up a suitable cultivation system. While autotrophic cultivations on bioreactor scale have a high technical demand, here a bottle cultivation system is used, which offers more process control than e.g. serum bottles while needed equipment is still at a minimum.

The potential and limitations of the setup are demonstrated through the cultivation of isopropanol-producing *Cupriavidus necator* as a model system. This gram-negative Knallgas bacterium has a versatile metabolism capable of utilizing a wide range of substrates, including CO₂ as its sole carbon source, with hydrogen serving as the electron donor. Hydrogen is oxidized by mainly two hydrogenases. The soluble hydrogenase transfers the obtained electron to NAD⁺, providing reduction equivalents, while the membrane-bound hydrogenase transfers the electrons to the respiratory chain with oxygen as the final electron acceptor. The resulting proton gradient fuels the ATP synthase, providing energy for the metabolism (Cramm, 2009). While *C. necator* is known as a native bioplastic producer, its product range has been expanded by genetic modifications and comprises alka(e)nes, sugars,

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terpenes, and ketones (Bi et al., 2013; Crépin et al., 2016; Hanko et al., 2022; Krieg et al., 2018; Müller et al., 2013). This offers a wide variety of value-added products derived from otherwise emitted CO₂.

The focus of this study is on isopropanol as the world's most widely used disinfectant, solvent, and promising blend-in to biofuels (Peralta-Yahya and Keasling, 2010). Currently, it is chemically produced using propene and benzene derived from fossil resources, resulting in the emission of 2.6 kgCO₂ per kilogram of isopropanol produced. In contrast, gas fermentation offers the potential for a carbon-negative production process (Liew et al., 2022).

Here, genetically engineered *C. necator* strains developed for heterotrophic isopropanol formation were used. In these strains, the last two steps of PHB synthesis were deleted, and the carbon flow was redirected over a heterologous expressed acetoacetate decarboxylase (*adc*) and alcohol dehydrogenase (*adh*) from *Clostridium* sp. Additionally, the native genes β -ketothiolase (*phaA*) and the native acetoacetyl-CoA-transferase (*ctf*), providing the precursor acetoacetate, are over-expressed. Product formation was initiated by e.g. nitrogen limitation, as described for PHB formation (Budde et al., 2011; Grousseau et al., 2014; Schlegel et al., 1961).

Even if the strains were well characterised under heterotrophic conditions, these results cannot be assumed to be the same under autotrophy due to different active metabolic pathways (Grousseau et al., 2014; Boy et al., 2023; Marc et al., 2017). For isopropanol formation, the carbon split ratio at acetyl-CoA is crucial as it determines how much of the carbon flow is led towards the citric acid cycle (TCA) to biomass formation and how much towards the targeted product. One precursor of acetyl-CoA, phosphoenolpyruvate, is possibly more tightly regulated under autotrophic conditions (Salinas et al., 2022). Additionally, succinate is a necessary reaction partner of the acetoacetyl-CoA-transferase providing the isopropanol precursor acetoacetate. Succinate again is a metabolite of the TCA which was upregulated under mixotrophic conditions compared to heterotrophy (Alagesan et al., 2018). Therefore, strains that performed well under heterotrophic conditions were characterised under autotrophic conditions.

Moreover, medium requirements may differ between heterotrophic and autotrophic cultivations due to these metabolic differences. Key enzymes under autotrophic conditions are the [NiFe]-hydrogenases, which contain nickel and iron in their catalytic site, and the CO₂-fixing enzyme Ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate-Carboxylase/Oxygenase (*Rubisco*) which requires the positively charged magnesium (Friedrich et al., 1981). The fixation of CO₂ by the Calvin cycle is further supported by the zinc-dependent carbon anhydrases, which convert CO₂ to and from bicarbonate (Lindskog, 1997).

This work highlights the process adjustments required when transitioning from heterotrophic to autotrophic conditions and compares the performance of both, using isopropanol formation by *C. necator* as a model system.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Preculture and strains

C. necator Re2133 (Δ phaB1B2B3C) (Budde et al., 2011) was mainly used to set up the cultivation conditions while the isopropanol-producing strains Re2133/pEG7b, Re2133/pEG8 and Re2133/pEG13 (Grousseau et al., 2014) were cultivated to demonstrate one potential application of the system.

The three isopropanol-forming strains carried the following plasmids: pEG8: pBBR1MCS-2[Kan^r][P_{lac}-RBS-*adc*-RBS-*adh*], pEG13: pBBR1MCS-2[Kan^r][P_{lac}-RBS-*phaA*-RBS-*ctfAB*-RBS-*adc*-RBS-*adh*-RBS-*adh*] and pEG7b: pBBR1MCS-2[Kan^r][P_{lac}-RBS-*phaA*-RBS-*ctfAB*-RBS-*adc*-RBS-*adh*]. While the β -ketothiolase *phaA* and the acetyl-CoA transferase *ctfAB* are native genes from *C. necator*, the acetoacetate decarboxylase *adc* and the alcohol dehydrogenase *adh* are codon-optimised versions derived from *Clostridium* sp.

The strains were stored at –80°C and streaked on rich medium plates where they were incubated for 3–5 d at 30 °C until single colonies were obtained. One colony was transferred to 5 mL of complex medium in a baffled 50 mL shake flask. It was grown to a final OD of 1.0 (around 17 h) to ensure a transfer in the late exponential growth phase. The second preculture step was conducted in a 250 mL baffled shake flask with 50 mL mineral medium containing 2 g L⁻¹ fructose and 0.5 g L⁻¹ NH₄Cl. It was inoculated with the first preculture to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.08 and cultivated to a final OD of 0.5 where fructose was depleted (around 17 h). This was confirmed by a rapid spectrometric method using Reflectoquant RQflex 20 (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) to ensure no sugar was transferred to the autotrophic main culture.

As rich medium 27.5 g L⁻¹ dextrose-free Bacto™ Tryptic soy was used, supplemented by 20 g L⁻¹ agar for solid media. The mineral medium with a pH of 6.8 contained 11.6 g L⁻¹ Na₂HPO₄ x 12H₂O, 5.2 g L⁻¹ NaH₂PO₄ x 2H₂O, 0.8 g L⁻¹ MgSO₄ x 7H₂O, 0.08 g L⁻¹ CaCl₂ x 2H₂O, 0.45 g L⁻¹ K₂SO₄, 0.04 g L⁻¹ NaOH, 0.033 mg L⁻¹ NiCl₂ x 6H₂O, 15 mg L⁻¹ FeSO₄ x 7H₂O, 2.4 mg L⁻¹ MnSO₄ x H₂O, 2.4 mg L⁻¹ ZnSO₄ x 7H₂O and 0.48 mg L⁻¹ CuSO₄ x 5H₂O. For all cultivation steps 10 mg L⁻¹ gentamicin was added and for strains containing plasmids bearing a kanamycin resistance, 100 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin was added to the culture. The main culture for strain comparison was performed with 1.0 g L⁻¹ NH₄Cl which was adequate to obtain 2 g L⁻¹ CDW. This biomass then served as an active biocatalyst for isopropanol formation under nitrogen depletion.

2.2. Shake flask cultivation

Main cultivations, both heterotrophic and autotrophic, were started with an OD of 0.05 and were cultivated at 30°C and 140 rpm in a shake incubator. They were conducted in 50 mL minimal medium including 10 mg L⁻¹ gentamicin, 100 mg L⁻¹ kanamycin and 1.0 g L⁻¹ NH₄Cl. For the heterotrophic cultivations additionally 28 g L⁻¹ fructose were added.

While the heterotrophic cultivations were conducted in 250 mL baffled shake flasks closed with cotton plugs, for the autotrophic cultivations 250 mL Schott bottles as shown in Fig. 1 were used. In the lower part of the bottle, a glass nozzle was attached which was closed by a silicon septum. This enabled sampling with a syringe and cannula without opening the lid. The bottles were closed with 2-valved lids whereby the tightness was ensured by a silicon ring between the bottle and lid. For added protection, the bottles were enclosed with a high-density polyethylene (HDPE) net.

To provide hydrogen, oxygen, and carbon dioxide during shake flask cultivation, a gas mixture was used to fill the headspace of the bottles and refilled when necessary. The commercial gas mixture contained 80.12 % hydrogen and 19.88 % carbon dioxide (AirLiquide, Bagneux, France) and was supplemented with pure oxygen. As the gas-to-liquid transfer is known to be one of the rate-limiting steps, an overpressure of 1.5 bar was applied to increase gas solubility.

Before starting cultivations, the closed bottle containing the inoculated medium was connected to a pump and vacuum was applied to remove air. To avoid sparks during the filling procedure no electrical gas mixing unit was used. Instead, the gas was introduced into the headspace up to a defined pressure which was measured by a manometer. First, the commercial H₂/CO₂ gas mixture was added up to a pressure between 1.2 and 1.4 bar, depending on the tested conditions. Then oxygen was added until a total overpressure of 1.5 bar was reached. During cultivations, the headspace pressure was measured by connecting the flask to the manometer. When the pressure fell to around 0.5 bar, the gas phase was refilled. For this, vacuum was applied to remove the residual gas phase and then the headspace was refilled with the new gas mixture up to the initial overpressure of 1.5 bar.

Fig. 1. Baffled Schott bottles closed with a 2-valved lid were used for autotrophic cultivations. During the gas filling process, the headspace was first emptied by a vacuum pump and then filled with a commercial H_2/CO_2 (80/20 mol%) mixture to a specific pressure. This was supplemented by a defined pressure of oxygen. Details on the used gas composition are given in the main text. During the experiment, pressure decrease was monitored by connecting the bottle to a manometer. The cultivation was carried out in a common laboratory shaker.

2.3. Analytics

During the cultivation the optical density (OD) at 600 nm was regularly measured to follow biomass formation, enabling the calculation of the growth rate. For cell dry weight (CDW) determination, samples were filtered through a 0.2 μm pore-size polyamide filter, dried at 60 °C and 200 mbar, and then weighed. The correlation between CDW and OD was established as $\text{CDW} = 2 \times \text{OD}$. All given biomass concentrations are calculated based on the measured OD.

For HPLC and ICP-MS analysis, samples were centrifuged at 13,200 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatant was filtered through a 0.2 μm pore-size hydrophilic filter. The concentrations of fructose, citrate, acetone, acetoacetate, pyruvate, isopropanol, and succinate were determined using an HPLC Waters e2695 (Waters, Milford, US) equipped with a 300 \times 7.8 mm HPX-87H Biorad Aminex column with a 30 \times 4.6 mm Cation H^+ cartridge pre-column (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). Separations were performed at a column temperature of 50 °C, and products were detected by a Refractive Index (RI) detector with the eluent being 2.5 mM H_2SO_4 at a flow rate of 0.5 mL min^{-1} .

Extracellular concentrations of nickel, iron, and zinc were measured using an Agilent 7700 Series ICP-MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, US). Scandium was used as an internal standard (1 ppm in 5 % HNO_3), and argon was applied as a carrier gas with a flow of 15 L min^{-1} . For analysis, the software ICP-MS MassHunter B.01.01 was used.

Extracellular nitrogen and magnesium concentrations were determined by higher-pressure ionic chromatography (HPIC) as described by Boy et al. (2021).

3. Results

3.1. Development of gas feeding strategy

The applicable gas mixtures for the experiments were limited by the available commercial gas mixture containing 80 % H_2 and 20 % CO_2 . To come closest to the optimal gas ratio of $\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 67\text{--}68/23\text{--}28/5\text{--}9$ (Morinaga et al., 1978; Yu and Lu, 2019) a gas composition of 63/20/17 mol% was tested for growing *C. necator* Re2133. This was compared to gas mixes containing lower oxygen concentrations –70/12/18 mol% and 74/8/18 mol% - to study their effect on growth (Fig. 2). The gas mixture containing 20 % oxygen inhibited growth. The gas composition of $\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 74/8/18$ mol% led to a faster initial growth rate, while with 70/12/18 mol% a comparable maximal growth rate of 0.09–0.13 h^{-1} was obtained. As described in the method section, the gas phase was renewed when the headspace overpressure dropped from 1.5 bar to around 0.5 bar. Even though the lowest tested oxygen concentration obtained the fastest growth, a change to the gas composition containing 12 % oxygen starting from the first refill achieved further improvement in growth (Fig. 3).

To identify the best refilling criteria, the headspace was replaced by a fresh gas mixture after the pressure fell from 1.5 bar to either 0.5, 1.0, or 1.25 bar, resulting in more frequent gas refills. For this experiment, the gas composition containing 8 % oxygen was used. Fig. 4 shows that a gas refill only after a pressure drop of one bar resulted in the highest growth rate of $\mu_{\text{max}} 0.13 \text{ h}^{-1}$ after 19 h. An earlier gas refill led to a μ_{max} of 0.09 h^{-1} with no further difference found between the refill at 1.0 bar or 1.25 bar. Since the decrease of headspace pressure reflects the metabolic activity (Figure S1), pressure-based gas refill allows a feeding strategy adapted to the needs of the cell.

When comparing the refill frequency, the influence of vacuum application and the applied overpressure of 1.5 bar as potential influencing factors were considered. To ensure that they did not negatively impact growth, heterotrophic cultivation was carried out in the flasks used for autotrophic cultivation. As a reference, one flask was closed with a cotton plug to allow gas exchange with ambient air. The other flasks were closed with airtight screw caps and filled with 0.5 bar air, and additionally 0.5 or 1.0 bar nitrogen. The resulting different total pressures of 0, 0.5, 1.0, or 1.5 bar and vacuum application during the refill process did affect neither the lag phase nor the maximal growth rates of 0.27–0.31 h^{-1} of the heterotrophic cultivations (Fig. 5).

Based on the results obtained so far, for the following cultivations an initial gas composition of $\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 74/8/18$ mol% was applied and the gas phase was replenished with a gas mix of $\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 70/12/18$ mol% when the headspace overpressure fell to around 0.5 bar. This process strategy was then transferred to evaluate isopropanol-producing *C. necator* strains.

3.2. Medium adaptation to autotrophic cultivation conditions

As discussed in the introduction, medium requirements might differ between autotrophic and heterotrophic conditions due to metabolic differences. For the heterotrophic reference cultivations, a medium containing 3.01 mg L^{-1} iron, and 0.55 mg L^{-1} zinc but without nickel addition was used (Grousseau et al., 2014). As the iron and zinc concentrations were in the range described in literature for autotrophic cultivations, only the nickel concentration was adjusted. The medium was completed with 8 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ nickel, recognizing its critical role in sustaining the activity of the hydrogenases and thus the autotrophic metabolism. This concentration was chosen based on autotrophic cultivations conducted on a bioreactor scale (Marc et al., 2017).

During the cultivation of the isopropanol-producing *C. necator* strains, after an exponential growth phase, product formation stopped abruptly after about 48 h (Fig. 6). ICP-MS measurements showed that the nickel concentration after 72 h was below the limit of detection of 2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. While neither the addition of only 140 mg L^{-1} of nitrogen nor

Fig. 2. Influence of gas composition during autotrophic shake flask cultivation of *C. necator* Re2133 on OD (a) and growth rate (b). The gas phase was refilled with the given composition when headspace pressure dropped from 1.5 bar to 0.5 bar. Cultivations were conducted in duplicates.

Fig. 3. Starting the autotrophic cultivation of *C. necator* Re2133 with a gas composition of H₂/O₂/CO₂ = 74/8/18 mol% and replacing it after the first bar pressure consumption with H₂/O₂/CO₂ = 70/12/18 mol% instead of 74/8/18 mol%, improved growth. Cultivations were conducted in duplicates.

16 μg L⁻¹ nickel restarted growth or product formation, the addition of nitrogen and nickel together restarted both (Figure S2).

A strategy similar to Repaske and Repaske, (1976) was employed to prevent nickel limitation in further cultivations. As they described an inhibiting nickel concentration of 58 μg L⁻¹ with maximum 29 μg L⁻¹ added at the beginning, here concentrations staying below this threshold were chosen. For further experiments, the nickel concentration was increased to 48 μg L⁻¹, with half of it added initially and the other half added during the mid-exponential growth phase. This approach effectively extended product formation to 120 h and doubled the obtained isopropanol concentration (Fig. 6). Moreover, with sufficient nickel provision, the standard deviation of triplicates was lower. At the end of cultivations conducted with 48 μg L⁻¹ nickel, 4–13 μg L⁻¹ residual nickel was quantified in the medium.

From the initially added 3.01 mg L⁻¹ iron, 0.07–0.11 mg L⁻¹ iron remained at the end of the experiment, indicating that it was not yet limiting but should be adjusted for prolonged biomass or product formation. The zinc concentration was reduced from 0.55 mg L⁻¹ to 0.06–0.16 mg L⁻¹, showing that the applied concentration was appropriate for the process. Initially, 79 mg L⁻¹ of magnesium was added. Throughout the cultivation period, the magnesium concentrations fluctuated but remained above 60 mg L⁻¹. Setting the element consumption in relation with the formed biomass in Cmol gives

Fig. 4. Influence of refilling frequency of a gas mixture of H₂/O₂/CO₂ of 74/8/18 mol% during autotrophic shake flask cultivation of *C. necator* Re2133 on the growth rate. Cultivations were conducted in duplicates.

Fig. 5. Application of up to 1.5 bar headspace overpressure during heterotrophic cultivation (4.35 g L^{-1} fructose, $0.28 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ NH}_4\text{Cl}$) of *C. necator* Re2133. Cultivations were conducted in duplicates.

Fig. 6. Impact of adding either $48 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ or $8 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of nickel on growth and product formation of *C. necator* Re2133/pEG8. The shaded area corresponds to the standard deviation of isopropanol concentration based on triplicates.

consumptions of $6.5 - 7.6 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{Nickel}}/\text{Cmol}_{\text{Biomass}}$, $514 - 569 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{iron}}/\text{Cmol}_{\text{Biomass}}$ and $65 - 73 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{zinc}}/\text{Cmol}_{\text{Biomass}}$.

3.3. Application of the cultivation system for strain characterisation

The improved cultivation conditions were applied to compare three promising isopropanol-producing strains *C. necator* Re2133/pEG8, Re2133/pEG13 and Re2133/pEG7b (Grousseau et al., 2014) under heterotrophic and autotrophic conditions. Fig. 7 shows that heterotrophic growth is twice as fast, with the maximum biomass concentration reached after nitrogen depletion at 12–18 h, compared to 34–38 h under autotrophic conditions. In the heterotrophic cultivation, isopropanol concentrations increased from the cultivation start, with product formation accelerating once growth stopped. When CO_2 was used as carbon source, product formation started later but showed the same behaviour. Due to the extended cultivation duration under autotrophic conditions, it was observed that isopropanol formation slowed down during the nitrogen-depleted phase but continued throughout the 144-h cultivation period.

Table 1 shows the key metrics for both cultivations. As mentioned above, the metabolic rates are faster when fructose is used as substrate compared to CO_2 , with the growth rate high under heterotrophic conditions being twice as high with $0.20\text{--}0.21 \text{ h}^{-1}$ compared to 0.10 h^{-1} .

This is also reflected in the overall productivity with $0.046\text{--}0.061 \text{ g}_{\text{IPA}} \text{ L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ in the heterotrophic cultivations, whereas over $58 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ I}_{\text{IPA}}$ was $0.017\text{--}0.025 \text{ g}_{\text{IPA}} \text{ L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ in the autotrophic flasks.

The differences between the three strains were more pronounced under heterotrophic conditions. Re2133/pEG7b exhibited slightly delayed growth during heterotrophic cultivation, which was not observed in autotrophy. While Re2133/pEG7b obtained a higher isopropanol concentration of 3.4 g L^{-1} than Re2133/pEG13 and Re2133/pEG8 with 2.6 and 2.5 g L^{-1} in heterotrophy, the difference between the three strains was not significant when using CO_2 as carbon source. Notably, the autotrophic cultivation system exhibited higher standard deviations, particularly in product formation.

Comparing the specific isopropanol yield $Y_{\text{IPA}/X}$ between heterotrophic and autotrophic conditions after 56–58 h would be biased due to the delayed onset of product formation in autotrophy. Additionally, since isopropanol continues to be formed during the nitrogen-depleted phase, specific yields increase with extended cultivation time. With CO_2 as carbon source a $Y_{\text{IPA}/X}$ of $0.9\text{--}1.1 \text{ g g}^{-1}$ after 144 h was reached.

Acetone is the direct precursor of isopropanol, thus a full conversion is envisaged. Observed acetone concentrations were comparable over all strains and cultivation modes with acetone concentrations increasing with isopropanol formation. In autotrophic conditions with a final acetone concentration of $52 \pm 8 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ of strain Re2133/pEG8, $61 \pm 4 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ of strain Re2133/pEG13 and $47 \pm 13 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ of strain Re2133/pEG7b, Re2133/pEG7b obtained the highest product-to-byproduct ratio.

4. Discussion

In this study, an autotrophic cultivation on shake flask scale was presented, providing an easy tool for strain comparison with low technical requirements. For an increased gas transfer, baffled bottles were employed and overpressure was applied. As the pressure decrease reflected metabolic activity it was used as a criterion for gas refill.

The cultivation conditions were optimised, and the ideal gas composition was determined. Growth was supported only at oxygen concentrations below 20%. This contrasts with the optimal gas composition for exponential growth of *C. necator*, which is typically given as $\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2/\text{CO}_2 = 5\text{--}7/1.5\text{--}2.5/1$, thus corresponding to an oxygen concentration of 20–24% (Morinaga et al., 1978, Ishizaki et al., 2001). Notably, Amer and Kim (2023) described growth at oxygen levels as high as 0.7 bar (47%) in *C. necator* ATCC 17697, using Hungate tubes. A higher gas transfer in the bottles used here can be assumed due to their baffles and larger diameter, but in general comparisons between

Fig. 7. Comparison of growth and isopropanol formation of *C. necator* Re2133/pEG8, Re2133/pEG13 and Re2133/pEG7b under optimised autotrophic (a) and heterotrophic (b) conditions. Figure (c) shows the isopropanol operon setup as published in Grousseau et al. (2014) with native *Cupriavidus* genes THL (β -keto-thiolase) and CTF (acetoacetyl-CoA-transferase) and codon-optimised *Clostridium* genes ADC (acetoacetate decarboxylase) and ADH (alcohol dehydrogenase). Cultivations were performed with $1.0 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ NH}_4\text{Cl}$ allowing a maximum biomass concentration of $2 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ CDW}$.

Table 1

Comparison of biomass, isopropanol and acetone formation by *C. necator* on shake flask scale under auto- and heterotrophic conditions. For autotrophic cultivation, values are given for 144 h as the end of the cultivation as well as for 58 h as a point comparable to the heterotrophic cultivation. Standard deviations are given for biological triplicates. Growth rates and biomass concentrations were calculated based on the measured OD.

		Re2133/pEG13		Re2133/pEG8		Re2133/pEG7b				
		autotrophic	hetero-trophic	autotrophic	hetero-trophic	autotrophic	hetero-trophic			
t	[h]	144	58	144	58	134	58	55		
μ	[h ⁻¹]	0.096 ± 0.003	0.215 ± 0.003	0.096 ± 0.002	0.212 ± 0.003	0.093 ± 0.003	0.198 ± 0.002	0.198 ± 0.002		
C _{IPA}	[g L ⁻¹]	2.22 ± 0.11	1.45 ± 0.17	1.83 ± 0.16	0.98 ± 0.20	2.46 ± 0.13	2.23 ± 0.45	1.30 ± 0.14	3.38 ± 0.20	
r _{IPA}	[g L ⁻¹ h ⁻¹]	0.015 ± 0.001	0.025 ± 0.003	0.013 ± 0.001	0.017 ± 0.003	0.044 ± 0.002	0.017 ± 0.004	0.023 ± 0.003	0.061 ± 0.004	
Y _{IPA/X}	[g g ⁻¹]	1.1 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	
Y _{acet/X}	[mg g ⁻¹]	29 ± 2	25 ± 7	38 ± 8	25 ± 4	15 ± 10	34 ± 2	20 ± 6	25 ± 7	49 ± 3
acet/	[g g ⁻¹]	0.027	0.037	0.034	0.029	0.032	0.031	0.021	0.034	0.034
IPA		± 0.003	± 0.006	± 0.004	± 0.006	± 0.015	± 0.002	± 0.003	± 0.010	± 0.001

different cultivation systems remain speculative without characterising gas transfer rates or measuring dissolved gas concentrations.

Different levels of susceptibility to oxygen may be attributed to the general stress level of the cells. Here, in contrast to Amer and Kim (2023), heterotrophic precultures were employed to reduce the required time for precultures. The substrate shift potentially induced a stress reaction, making cells more vulnerable to additional stress factors (Serna-García et al., 2024). This could explain the higher sensitivity to elevated oxygen concentrations at the beginning of the cultivations as it was demonstrated that 8 % O₂ promoted higher initial growth rates, whereas 12 % O₂ was more beneficial during the later cultivation stages.

Additionally, here it was shown that overpressure of up to 1.5 bar did not negatively impact cell growth, aligning with Amer and Kim (2023) finding of no negative effect of a total pressure of up to 3 bar.

When transitioning from a heterotrophic to an autotrophic cultivation process, it is essential to ensure that the medium composition is appropriately adapted. The here presented uptake of elements per Cmol of biomass, isopropanol and acetone can serve as a guideline for the amount of nickel, iron and zinc required for the envisaged process. It has been demonstrated that nickel as cofactor in the active center of

hydrogenases is particularly critical for autotrophic isopropanol formation while not needed under heterotrophic conditions.

A comparative analysis was performed under both heterotrophic and autotrophic conditions to gain deeper insights into the engineered isopropanol-producing strains. With CO₂ as a carbon source, no significant differences in growth rates were observed between *C. necator* Re2133 ($0.10 \pm 0.01 \text{ h}^{-1}$) and the three isopropanol-producing strains ($0.09\text{--}0.10 \text{ h}^{-1}$). This contrasts with Garrigues et al. (2020), where better-controlled bioreactor conditions yielded a growth rate of $0.05 \pm 0.01 \text{ h}^{-1}$ for *C. necator* Re2133/pEG7b, while the PHB-negative strain *C. necator* Re2133 exhibited a higher rate of 0.13 h^{-1} , attributed to the metabolic burden of isopropanol production, which was not confirmed here. The exponential growth and high product concentrations obtained, underline that the used flask system effectively supported unrestricted growth.

For autotrophic cultivations, a decrease in productivity over the cultivation duration can be observed during the nitrogen-depleted phase. As described in the literature, at the bioreactor scale this can be easily improved by e.g. nitrogen drip feeding to support a residual μ after the exponential growth phase (Grousseau et al., 2013; Marc et al.,

2017).

The acetone-to-isopropanol conversion was efficient in all three strains, with minimal final acetone concentrations observed ($0.09 \pm 0.02 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ in heterotrophy and $0.05 \pm 0.01 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ in autotrophy), so the effect of the additional alcohol dehydrogenase in Re2133/pEG13 does not come to play under these conditions. In contrast, the over-expression of the native genes *thl* and *ctf* in Re2133/pEG7b and Re2133/pEG13, compared to Re2133/pEG8, resulted in higher product concentrations under both heterotrophic and autotrophic conditions, irrespective of the carbon source used.

Autotrophic growth was approximately half as fast as heterotrophic growth, with productivity reduced by 46–62 % (data from 58 h). This reduction may stem from the difference in the specific growth rates and an extended lag phase, as cells adapted to a new carbon source following inoculation from a heterotrophic preculture. Additionally, gas transfer remains a key bottleneck in autotrophic cultivations, and despite the pressure applied, it may be more restrictive at the bottle scale compared to bioreactors with better process control. Autotrophic metabolism also exhibits inherent challenges, such as slow CO_2 -fixation with wasteful side reactions catalyzed by RuBisCo. Ultimately, autotrophic processes offer the potential to valorize CO_2 -rich gas streams, and wide industrial implementation will depend on the trade-off between process efficiency and substrate costs.

The highest isopropanol concentration in autotrophic shake flasks obtained in this study was 2.8 g L^{-1} with *C. necator* Re2133/pEG7b which demonstrates the effective cultivation parameters chosen, especially when considering that most publications regarding autotrophic cultivation of *C. necator* on flask scale were proof-of-concepts obtaining final product concentrations below 0.5 g L^{-1} (Krieg et al., 2018, Li et al., 2019, Przybylski et al., 2015). Also, compared to the achieved isopropanol concentration of 3.5 g L^{-1} likewise obtained with *C. necator* Re2133/pEG7b but under better-controlled conditions on a bioreactor scale, the product concentration obtained here is promising (Garrigues et al., 2020). In general, the highest isopropanol concentration with *C. necator* was reached in heterotrophic bioreactor cultivation with 16 g L^{-1} (Marc et al., 2017). Recently, the first industrial-scale isopropanol-producing fermentation process was published with a productivity of $3 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ cultivating the anaerobic *Clostridium autoethanogenum* using CO as carbon source (Liew et al., 2022). More research is needed to obtain comparable yields under aerobic conditions with CO_2 and the here presented methodology will be valuable for this.

5. Summary and conclusion

This study presents an approach for autotrophic bottle cultivation with low technical effort, but sufficient process control for an efficient process. Adjusting the gas composition in the headspace together with measuring its pressure allows monitoring the metabolic activity adapted to the needs of the cells. It ensures a reproducible setup, allowing replicates, and is thus beneficial for strain comparison and medium optimization. The necessity for medium adaptation when transferring a process from heterotrophic to autotrophic conditions was discussed in which especially the importance of nickel for product formation was pointed out. By applying the parameters optimized here for the culture of *C. necator*, an isopropanol concentration of 2.2 g L^{-1} was obtained.

Aerobic gas fermentation is a promising alternative route to transform the currently existing petroleum-based industry. The method presented herein will contribute to simplifying research on it by lowering the technical hurdle of getting started with aerobic autotrophic cultivation for laboratories so far focused on heterotrophic cultivation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: S. Guillouet reports financial support was provided by European Union. If

there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.jbiotec.2025.03.011.

Data availability

Data will be available on request after approval by the consortium of the EU project ConCO2rde.

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